

Preparation of Bi₁₂GeO₂₀ Nanocrystalline Structures

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The problem of creating new functional materials with adjustable optical properties used in membrane technologies, optics, quantum electronics, analytical instrumentation, and photonics is of great importance. The so-called porous glasses are promising matrices for such materials due to their unique set of adsorption, diffusion, optical, and other characteristics combined with adjustable structural parameters of the nanoscale range [1,2]. When substances with active physical properties are introduced into porous matrices, the functional capabilities of the introduced components are significantly expanded and the practical significance of such structures increases significantly [3,4].

In our studies, we use nanoporous Al₂O₃ and Si membranes, both purchased from SmartMembranes (Germany) and membranes manufactured by ourselves at the same company.

The polycrystalline fine powder Bi₁₂GeO₂₀ (BGO) was applied to the surface of the Si and Al₂O₃ samples and evenly distributed on its surface. Pieces of the single-crystal BGO sample were preliminarily crushed mechanically and carefully ground in an agate mortar for several hours to a fine powder. The nanocrystalline matrices were pre-annealed at a temperature of □ 200□C to purify them from foreign organic compounds.

The melting of BGO powder on the surface of Si and Al₂O₃ matrices was carried out in a muffle resistive furnace at a temperature of 950□C. The matrices were kept at this temperature for 30 min to saturate the pores with BGO melt. Further crystallization took place during spontaneous cooling in a switched-off furnace. It is important to choose a substrate for nanoporous matrices, which, in the case of melt "leakage," will allow separation of the nanocrystalline structure from the substrate. We used mica plates.

As a result of the synthesis of BGO in the pores of Si and Al₂O₃ matrices, it was found that the Al₂O₃ matrix practically crumbled. X-ray diffraction analysis showed that Al₂O₃ crystallized and cracked. While in the pores of the Si matrix, the formation of the BGO crystal structure was confirmed.

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